

A DYNAMIC STOCHASTIC APPROACH FOR PREDICTING THE PRODUCTION CAPACITY OF AN INDUSTRIAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT: *Time loss in the manufacturing process of a production line reduces productivity and harms the system's brand image and long-term performance. The present research focuses on the use of scientific analysis and diagnostic techniques to correct current errors and to anticipate the future behaviour of a system. This paper proposes a stochastic approach, FORCAST-FBM, which is based on a hybridization of three methods: Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), Bayesian Networks, and Monte Carlo Simulation. Our objective is to address a crucial issue in industrial production systems—namely, the forecasting of the quantity to be produced within a probable time frame during an upcoming production period. This approach plays a key role in production planning and management development. The proposed solution applies to any system in which production follows a chronological sequence across parallel production facilities, where components move along an automated path with no backward flow.*

Keywords: *Industrial production forecasting, Monte Carlo simulation, Bayesian networks, FMEA.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing industry is a rapidly evolving sector whose success depends on the efficiency of its components, such as production facilities, workers, and other elements of the production system. Workshop and production managers rely on key performance indicators [1] (including productivity, reliability, availability, failure rate, overall equipment effectiveness, etc.) to continuously assess the current production states and implement necessary adjustments to minimize potential losses (time, budget, inventory, etc.) and optimize resource utilization [2]. Industrial revolutions have so far led to paradigm shifts in the field of production, largely driven by advances in information technologies [3]. In recent years, however, industries, researchers, and decision-makers have increasingly sought to enhance continuous improvement by leveraging data science [4], as well as the way the industry works [5]. The occurrence of random events that affect the progress of a manufacturing process is numerous, whether operational, financial, or otherwise, and difficult to control due to the inherent complexity of the process. Consequently, production system managers are increasingly urged to move away from traditional management approaches and to ensure effective production control through the adoption of new tools based on advanced analytical techniques [6], such as

FMEA (Failure Mode, Effects, and Criticality Analysis) [7], to capture their contributions to system development. Moreover, data statistics and analytical studies rely primarily on company records and reports. Therefore, modelling is required to understand and represent the system's data in relation to its stochastic behaviour, and to evaluate it using simulation techniques [8], thereby enabling the interpretation of possible scenarios that may occur in real-world conditions. Forecasting is a general study of a given situation that uses historical data as the main source of information, allowing, through deduction, computation, or scientific measurement, the prediction of a system's future evolution. In other words, forecasting consists of estimating what will occur at time $t + I$, based on knowledge and observation collected before time t .

Forecasting the performance of industrial systems is a major research area with numerous applications across industrial production, transportation, meteorology, and other fields. Current forecasting models are largely based on machine learning and deep neural network techniques, which rely on extensive historical datasets to predict future trends and values. These models have demonstrated outstanding predictive performance; however, their high computational costs limit their practical application [9]. Forecasting has a wide range of real-world applications, notably in industrial production systems, such as production management [10],

inventory management [11], system control [11], energy management [12], and maintenance management [13], as well as in the field of business economics [14], among others.

2. MOTIVATION AND CONTRIBUTION

In an industrial production system, the availability of production machinery is a critical parameter that supports strategic decision-making regarding the system's future state. This study provides a valuable contribution to the industrial sector, particularly in contexts such as gas bottle manufacturing, by highlighting several practical advantages. The main objective of this work is to simulate, through multiple iterations, the stochastic behaviour of the system based on historical data, to identify possible disturbance scenarios within the production process, and to build a comprehensive historical database of system performance. The ultimate goal is to forecast the quantity likely to be produced during the next production period ($t + 1$), thereby calculating production capacity dynamics and dependent on the system variables recorded in the previous period (t). This predictive capability aims to assist production managers in making timely decisions, increasing productivity, and minimizing unforeseen costs (such as additional time or budget overheads) during industrial operations. The overall purpose is to ensure that production is completed within the time constraints agreed upon with the client, without extension, while maintaining the company's competitiveness within its market environment.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Designing production systems that are practically safe and robust, whether in terms of technology used, personnel involved, or equipment employed, is important; however, it must also be acknowledged that even in a "perfect" system, malfunctions such as failures or shutdowns are inevitable [15]. Therefore, a forecasting approach is essential to anticipate and resolve potential problems in advance, allowing the system to be rebalanced in the future [16]. Modern production systems require accurate forecasts to achieve excellence in operation and planning, as well as to manage resources in production workshops optimally [15].

Forecasting in production systems has thus become a critical issue in industrial contexts. Numerous contributions have been made in this field through different methodological approaches. A probabilistic approach based on Bayesian networks has been developed to predict energy consumption in specific systems [17],[18]. Daibiao et al. [19] considered Bayesian networks as a reliable quality

tool to analyse and assess the causes and impacts of workplace accidents within manufacturing processes. To improve diagnostic accuracy and provide rational explanations for system fault occurrences, a fault diagnosis method using Bayesian networks has also been proposed [19]. Forecasting in industrial production systems is essential for optimizing operations and ensuring maximum efficiency. It enables the anticipation of events that may occur within the system – such as production demands, product sales, production volumes, raw material needs, equipment failures, or economic indicators – to readjust resource planning and minimize costs [20]. Forecasting assists decision-makers at short, medium-, and long-term levels. Short-term [17] forecasting, extending up to 72 hours in advance, is applied to system operation, economic allocation, and unit engagement [21],[22]. Medium-term forecasting, from several days to about a week ahead [21], is generally used to optimize maintenance activities. Finally, long-term forecasting – spanning several months to a year or more – is used for strategic planning [22],[23].

Several forecasting models commonly used in the literature are categorized as either quantitative or qualitative. According to [24], quantitative forecasting models are generally divided into three main types: machine learning (ML) based methods, statistical methods, and hybrid methods. Among ML-based models, one can find artificial intelligence techniques such as artificial and deep neural networks [25],[26], Petri networks [27], and genetic algorithms [28]. Statistical methods mainly include time series models [29] and regression models [30]. Hybrid methods combine two or more different methodologies [17],[28],[31],[32]. Stochastic models, which rely on probabilistic techniques such as Markov models [33], simulation models [34], and Bayesian models [35],[36], are also widely discussed. Each of these approaches has shown success under specific conditions. The choice of a forecasting approach largely depends on several critical parameters, including production history, the nature of the manufacturing process, and the system's operating environment.

4. METHODS

This research employs three stochastic scientific analysis techniques to develop a forecasting approach for production time, with the goal of readjusting the daily production quantity so that customer orders are completed within the agreed deadlines. In this context, the FMEA (Failure Mode, Effects, and Criticality Analysis) technique is used primarily to identify all potential events or causes that may occur during the manufacturing process,

which are then exploited as variables to construct a system model using the Bayesian network method. The resulting model is subsequently simulated

through the Monte Carlo simulation technique to explore possible production scenarios within the system.

Figure 1. Diagram of the FORCAST-BL approach

Before any analytical work, a descriptive approach is required to identify and understand the behaviour of the system under study. The aim is to summarise all the operational states of the system, as well as the events that may cause disturbances in the normal operation of the manufacturing process. Consider, for instance, a section of the production system dedicated to gas bottle manufacturing (BAG).

This section includes two production lines where disturbances such as shutdowns or degradations frequently occur. Figure 2 provides a global view of the production system, allowing the synthesis and organization of information in a structured and hierarchical manner. The accompanying table explains the components represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. BAG system block diagram

Table 1. Components of the production system

Component	Description
BS2	Raw material used to produce the upper and lower shells of the bottle
Fd	Raw material used to produce the base and the collar of the bottle
ES	Upper shell of the bottle (top end)
EI	Lower shell of the bottle (bottom end)
C1	Collar of the bottle
Pd	Base of the bottle

The states – corresponding to the system’s activity – reflect the real-time operational situation of the machines and production lines. The operational states of the BAG manufacturing process are summarized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Operational states of an industrial production system.

Table 2. Legend of the operational states of an industrial production system

System State	Description
E1	The manufacturing process operates under normal conditions
E2	Degradation of production rates due to critical events such as failures, etc.
E3	The process is in a complete shutdown.

Monitoring these states is essential for ensuring performance, efficiency, and effective decision-making. In the field of production management, production systems can be modelled using system variables such as machinery, operators, and raw

materials. In this context, the operational states are governed by a set of variables that can influence the behaviour of the manufacturing process. Accordingly, in our case study, Table 3 defines the following variables:

Table 3: System Variables

System State	Task on the Production Plan	Role	System Variable
E1	Production Order	Launching of production	Ord-Prod
	Production Execution	Production of lower shells	Pr-EI
		Production of upper shells	Pr-ES
		Production of collars	Pr-CI
		Production of bases	Pr-Pd
E2	Disturbances	Hydraulic failure	FAILURE
		Electrical failure	
		Pneumatic failure	
		Electronic failure	
		Mechanical failure	
E3	Malfunction: "Total system shutdown"	Lack of compressed air	M-AC
		General power outage	M-EN
		Lack of raw material (e.g., steel strip, BS2 sheet, etc.)	M-BDG

From the understanding of the sequence of production operations of the system (case study), the results obtained in the synoptic diagram (after

several modelling iterations), knowledge acquired from Table 2, and the consultation of experts, the following dynamic model can be defined:

Figure 4: Bayesian Model of the BAG System.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of performance forecasting for systems, where the objective is to predict their future behaviour, an initial vector of variable values (based on the recorded historical data) representing the

initial conditions of the system's state to predict the next state $t+1$ must be defined. In our case study, varying scenarios are generated within the range of system variable values recorded during period t . A sequence of instructions is then executed to estimate the possible time loss during the following period ($t+1$).

Table 4. Configuration of Variables

Variables	ComputationalFunction	Meaning
Pr-EI	Read Pr-EI(Min _{WT} ,Max _{WT})	Insert the minimum and maximum values of lost time (WT) in the <i>Lower Stamping</i> unit.
TPP_{EI}	Alea (TTP _{EI} [Min _{EI} , Max _{EI}])	Probability of disturbance in the <i>Lower Stamping</i> unit.
Pr-ES	Read Pr-ES(Min _{WT} ,Max _{WT})	Insert the minimum and maximum values of lost time (WT) in the <i>Upper Stamping</i> unit.
TPP_{ES}	Alea (TTP _{ES} [Min _{ES} , Max _{ES}])	Probability of disturbance in the <i>Upper Stamping</i> unit.
Pr-Pd	Read Pr-Pd(Min _{WT} ,Max _{WT})	Insert the minimum and maximum values of lost time (WT) in the <i>Base</i> unit.
TPP_{Pd}	Alea (TTP _{Pd} [Min _{Pd} , Max _{Pd}])	Probability of disturbance in the <i>Base</i> production unit.
Pr-CI	Read Pr-CI(Min _{WT} ,Max _{WT})	Insert the minimum and maximum values of lost time (WT) in the <i>Neck Ring</i> unit.
TPP_{CI}	Alea (TTP _{CI} [Min _{CI} , Max _{CI}])	Probability of disturbance in the <i>Neck Ring</i> unit.
TPP_{M-AC}	≈ 0.003	Probability of production shutdown due to lack of compressed air.
TPP_{M-EN}	≈ 0.002	Probability of production shutdown due to power outage.
TPP_{M-BDG}	≈ 0.002	Probability of production shutdown due to lack of budget.
IPPPS_{PROD}	Max (TPP-EI, TPP-ES, TPP-Pd, TPP-CI, TPP _{M-AC} , TPP _{M-EN} , TPP _{M-BDG})	Probability of production disturbance for a given scenario.
PPPI_{PROD}	Max (TTPS _{PROD})	Probability of production disturbance per iteration of 300 possible values.

Production simulation is a computer-based modelling technique that recreates a real manufacturing system to analyse and optimize its performance. It allows the exploration of multiple scenarios, visualization of production flows, reduction of experimentation costs, and improvement of efficiency by identifying bottlenecks and inefficiencies before they affect actual production.

A simulation run is launched to test possible time-loss scenarios within the production system. This helps predict the behaviour of the manufacturing process in the next period before it occurs in real conditions. The main objective is to adjust the system's parameters to ensure smooth and efficient production. The result of our simulation – for a single iteration – generates 300 scenarios.

Table 5. Simulation results of the system variables.

Scenario No	TPP _{EI} (%)	TPP _{ES} (%)	TPP _{Pd} (%)	TPP _{CI} (%)	TPP _{M-AC} (%)	TPP _{M-EN} (%)	TPP _{M-BDG} (%)	PPPS _{PROD} (%)
1	0.02666667	0.07589744	0.03282051	0.01230769	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07589744
2	0.09230769	0.07179487	0.0574359	0.01435897	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.09230769
3	0.09641026	0.06974359	0.0225641	0.03897436	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.09641026
4	0.09435897	0.03897436	0.01641026	0.01435897	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.09435897
5	0.01435897	0.06358974	0.04923077	0.04102564	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.06358974
6	0.01230769	0.07179487	0.06974359	0.04307692	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07179487
7	0.06564103	0.06769231	0.04307692	0.03282051	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.06769231
8	0.04102564	0.04102564	0.0574359	0.04512821	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.0574359
9	0.01641026	0.04717949	0.03897436	0.01435897	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.04717949
10	0.03487179	0.07179487	0.05333333	0.04307692	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07179487
11	0.06153846	0.02666667	0.05948718	0.01230769	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.06153846
12	0.07589744	0.03076923	0.06974359	0.0225641	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07589744
13	0.1025641	0.0225641	0.07179487	0.05128205	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.1025641
14	0.02871795	0.03282051	0.0574359	0.01846154	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.0574359
15	0.07384615	0.04717949	0.04717949	0.03897436	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07384615
16	0.08	0.04307692	0.06974359	0.02051282	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.08
17	0.07384615	0.04512821	0.05128205	0.04307692	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07384615
18	0.05128205	0.07179487	0.04102564	0.01435897	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07179487
19	0.07384615	0.05333333	0.06564103	0.05128205	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07384615
20	0.07179487	0.04512821	0.01846154	0.03487179	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.07179487
21	0.1025641	0.05128205	0.01846154	0.01435897	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.1025641
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300	0.06564103	0.05538462	0.05538462	0.02051282	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.06564103
PPPI_{PROD}								0.1025641

The exploitation of the obtained model (Figure 4) and the system variable values across the production facilities made it possible to define the forecast of production availability through the following weighted tree.

In general, simulation iteration is not sufficient to fully read and understand a system. Therefore, repeating the simulation N times is crucial to broaden the overall understanding of the manufacturing process behaviour. This helps decision-makers establish a confidence interval

([minimum scenario value to maximum scenario value]) for each variable for the system's production, and to propose corrective actions for problems that could hinder the next production period. In our case study, it is possible to freely repeat the simulation of the manufacturing process behaviour. 300 scenarios are generated for iteration, where each one provides possible value ranges – such as machine downtime, system state probabilities, and potential new quantities to be produced, among others.

Table 6: Forecast of the probabilities of the system variables.

Probabilities of the model variables	Calculation law	Results for the case study	
		Forecast for period t+1: 1st iteration	Forecast for period t+1: N iterations
P(E1)	= Min (P(Pr-ES E1), P(Pr-EI E1), P(Pr-CI E1), P(Pr-Pd E1)) = 1-(P(E2) + P(E3))	0.93	[0.93...0.97]
P(E2)	= Max (P(Pr-ES E2), P(Pr-EI E2), P(Pr-CI E2), P(Pr-Pd E2)) = 1-(P(E1) + P(E3))	0.067	[0.03...0.07]
P(E3)	= Max(P(M-AC), P(M-EN), P(M-Bdg)) = 1-(P(E1) + P(E2))	0.003	[0.03...0.05]
P(Pr-ES E1)	$= \sum \frac{HPN Pr - ES}{TO}$	0.93	[0.93...0.97]
P(Pr-EI E1)	$= \sum \frac{HPN Pr - EI}{TO}$	0.93	[0.93...0.99]
P(Pr-CI E1)	$= \sum \frac{HPN Pr - CI}{TO}$	0.93	[0.93...0.98]
P(Pr-Pd E1)	$= \sum \frac{HPN Pr - Pd}{TO}$	0.95	[0.95...0.99]
P(Pr-ES E2)	$= \frac{(\sum HPN Pr - ES) - (\sum HPP Pr - ES)}{TO}$	0.07	[0.03...0.07]
P(Pr-EI E2)	$= \frac{(\sum HPN Pr - EI) - (\sum HPP Pr - EI)}{TO}$	0.07	[0.01...0.07]
P(Pr-CI E2)	$= \frac{(\sum HPN Pr - CI) - (\sum HPP Pr - CI)}{TO}$	0.07	[0.02...0.07]
P(Pr-Pd E2)	$= \frac{(\sum HPN Pr - Pd) - (\sum HPP Pr - Pd)}{TO}$	0.05	[0.01...0.05]
P(M-MAC E3)	$= \sum \frac{tAS_{(M-AC)}}{TO}$	0.003	[0.03...0.05]
P(M-EN E3)	$= \sum \frac{tAS_{(EN)}}{TO}$	0.002	[0.01...0.05]
P(M-Bdg E3)	$= \sum \frac{tAS_{Bdg}}{TO}$	0.002	[0.01...0.02]
Production forecast for period t+1		355	[320...370]

Based on the results obtained from the Bayesian model (Table 6), it is possible to forecast a production quantity $\in [320 \dots 370]$ gas bottles (BAGs) per day during period n+1. The maximum system capacity (i.e., the production rate of the installations) can reach up to 390 BAGs per day, whereas the current production plan (defined in period n) requires 315 BAGs per day. Accordingly, production managers should:

- Schedule maintenance to correct the condition of the production installations to reduce the occurrence of events that may lower the system's availability rate.
- Readjust the production quantity to $\in [320 \dots 370]$ BAGs per day to deliver the customer's order within the contractual deadline.

Our approach, FORCAST-FBM, aims to create a database of system variables to forecast the feasible production volume and dynamically schedule the system's working hours according to the availability of production installations at each time interval, while accounting for potential disturbances (shutdown or slowdowns) of each machine. To ensure the reliability and relevance of the data used

in the model's development, rigorous analytical techniques are applied. This study uses a set of stochastic analysis methods to predict the necessary production quantity required to meet delivery deadlines.

Flexibility is introduced by the approach to extend historical data through Monte Carlo simulation scenarios: In previous studies, data sources for Bayesian networks were mainly based on questionnaires and expert evaluations [23]. To address data discontinuity, fuzzy functions were used within Bayesian networks to transform discrete data into continuous data, making them closer to real-world conditions [37]. In our study, simulation is used to generate possible time-based values by determining minimum and maximum values from the historical data of a real system. This allows the definition of time intervals that help better understand the behaviour of the manufacturing process.

Flexibility is introduced by the approach to establish a realistic production plan through simulation:

Production scheduling is a key task in any industrial production system. It involves determining an optimized task schedule so that the results achieved over time best satisfy predefined objectives. Simulation techniques combine the variables that influence and control a manufacturing process to measure system stability and find a cost-effective production plan [38]. The Monte Carlo simulation enables multi-objective optimization to identify near-optimal production schedules. A previous study proposed a simulation-based approach for batch production systems with the goal of finding optimized work plans [39]. Our proposed method assists managers in determining the required production quantity, through simulation, to compensate for previously recorded delays and create a dynamic production plan that meets the daily requirements (*day j*) while correcting issues observed in the past period (*day j-1*).

Flexibility is introduced by the approach in defining system variables through FMEA (Failure Mode, Effects, and Criticality Analysis): The FMEA method involves performing a functional analysis to identify potential failure modes, their causes, and their effects on product or process performance.

Delage *et al.* applied FMEA to assess theoretical risks associated with a process to justify implementing a specific tool (the integration of smart pumps) into their system [39]. Another study [40] demonstrated that FMEA analysis can identify weaknesses in a new process following potential technical modifications to a system. In our contribution, we applied the FMEA method to identify the causes of potential failures in the production process and defined them as random variables in the system. The main objective is to establish a Bayesian model specifically adapted to our problem.

5. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

In conclusion, the scheduling of industrial production time is a key factor in supporting decision-making for managers who aim to operate efficiently. Mastering the production process not only optimizes resource utilization to achieve defined output targets but also ensures compliance with delivery deadlines committed to clients. Moreover, by improving efficiency, production managers can anticipate and manage potential disruptions, thereby minimizing downtime losses. For demonstration purposes, the proposed approach was applied to a simplified continuous manufacturing system for gas bottles (BAGs). This system includes four workstations and involves re-entrant flows, machine breakdowns, and recurrent

supply interruptions (raw materials, energy, etc.). Implementing our tool highlights the potential of using analytical and diagnostic techniques to enhance system behaviour, operational dynamics, and the overall efficiency of manufacturing facilities. The obtained results guide industrial systems toward improved productivity and optimized manufacturing processes through reduced downtime and mitigated disturbances. Our approach, embodied in the FORCAST-FBM tool, is a computational solution that captures the stochastic behaviour of production installations using real-world operational data (period *n*): lost production time per installation, delivery deadlines, quantities produced, and quantities remaining to produce. This enables the forecasting of the feasible output for the next period (*n+1*) to ensure timely delivery. FORCAST-FBM helps enhance overall production efficiency and supports managers in transitioning from theoretical production to realistic production management.

Finally, because nothing is perfect, we want the idea behind this work will be applied to systems with different architectures, industrial architectures for manufacturing companies, using other analysis techniques, especially those of artificial intelligence: Transfer learning, reinforcement learning, Another perspective on this work concerns the formalization of interactions between the company's production system and its environment. An important consideration concerns the collection, the treatment, and its exchange at the production workshop level. A more operational perspective is the wider use of the FORCAST-FBM approach, especially for the establishment and operation of a system of predictive performance indicators, to envision, in time, a multidimensional future for the company.

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